

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES IN INCREASING COCOON QUALITY

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Annotation. The article presents the main indicators of cocoons grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and foreign countries with developed cocoons, which shows the relatively low quality of cocoons grown in Uzbekistan and ways to improve it.

Introduction. The transition of the economy of the Republic to market relations requires improving the quality of agricultural products and bringing them to a level that can compete in the world market. In this regard, the workers of the silk industry have an important task, such as the production of cocoons that meet the requirements of quality and world standards. In order to solve this problem properly, it is necessary to achieve strict preparation of silkworm cocoons with clean, well-spun, long and thin fibers, flawless cocoons, strictly adhering to the silkworm feeding techniques. Unfortunately, batches of industrial cocoons grown, even in breeding cocoon groups, are known to contain a large number of defective cocoons and are delivered to cocoon receiving points.

The presence of defective cocoons in the delivered cocoon batches leads to an increase in the number of non-standard and unusable cocoons and economic damage to the cocoons. At the same time, defective cocoons lead to a decrease in silk raw material and a deterioration in the quality of silk fiber. Due to this, the cost of raw silk produced in silk factories in Uzbekistan is very low.

When considering the quality of the cocoon, first of all, it is assumed that the silk shell is a smooth whiteness, free from any stains and defects, uniform in shape and size.

There are a number of data on the cocoons of mulberry silkworms and the presence of variegated cocoons in the obtained crop, as well as its appearance and morphological features. Including E.B.Rubinov (1989), U.N.Nasirillaev (1993), S.Navro'zov (1993), E.X.Tojiev (1999), N.A.Akhmedov (2004), N.A.Akhmedov, A.Abdurahmanov (2006) described the information on the

cultivation and sorting of cocoons, the reception and storage of cocoons in the cocoon, the classification of cocoons according to their external characteristics. Given the urgency of the problem, we focused our research on studying and analyzing the quality of cocoons grown, determining the proportion of varietal cocoons, identifying the main types, quantity and causes of defective cocoons. In recent years, the share of cocoon production in the country has increased to 21-22 thousand tons a year. However, the variety of prepared cocoons decreased sharply and increased to 17-21%, and in some districts to 27-30%. This is equal to the amount of cocoons grown by at least two regions. In countries where cocoons are grown, the figure is 4-5%. Therefore, the cost of raw silk produced in the country is twice cheaper than in foreign countries, creating a number of difficulties in the export of cocoons grown in the country, the initial processing of cocoons and spinning in silk factories.

In recent years, 25,000 tons of cocoons have been grown in the country, yielding 48-50 kg of worms per box. The amount of low-grade and low-grade cocoons is more than 50%, the yield of silk from dry cocoons is 32-33% and the length of the cocoons is 800-850 meters. Of course, such indicators do not satisfy either the domestic or foreign markets.

Another major reason for the Uzbek government to make a number of decisions on further development of silk production is that the price of our dry cocoons in the world market is 2.5-3 and raw silk is 12-13 US dollars, which is twice cheaper than Chinese cocoons and silk. The main reason for this is the quality and productivity of cocoons, the low technological performance of raw silk. This can also be seen from the numbers below.

1-table

The main indicators of cocoons grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and foreign countries with developed silkworm breeding.

№	Indicators of the cocoon	In Uzbekistan	In China	In Japan
1	Variety of cocoons,%	70-72	95-96	97-98
2	First grade cocoons,%	40-42	93-94	95
3	Silk output,%	32-33	40-42	43-44
4	Length of continuous spinning of silk, m	350-500	800-900	950-1000
5	The amount of cocooning,%	70-72	80-83	85-87

The competitive quality of the cocoons, raw materials and fabrics produced depends on the productive breeds of silkworms, their feeding techniques and the technology of cocoon production and primary processing. The quality of silk obtained from high-quality cocoons is also high, and high-quality fabrics are produced from high-quality silk.

25-28% of cocoons grown in the country, 30-35% in some districts and regions are cocoons without varieties. There are a number of reasons for this. In particular, farm managers do not pay attention to silkworm breeding and do not feel responsible without understanding its essence. Failure to distribute in a timely manner, lack of space for worm feeding, and non-compliance with agronomic rules are clear examples of this.

Based on the reasons mentioned above, the factors affecting the quality of cocoons and the violation of agro-technical rules have a significant impact on the quality of cocoons, and it is very important to determine the most common types and quantities of defective cocoons.

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